

Open-Ended Labs (OEL)

CONTENTS:

- Acknowledgement.....2
- Title.....3
- Abstract.....3
- Problem statement.....3
- Introduction.....4
- Working Principle.....4
- Model Descriptions.....6
- Application of Hydraulic Excavator.....6
- Working.....7
- Analysis.....7
- Sample Calculation7
- Conclusion8
- Comments9
- Modification10
- Reference.....11

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1: Model.....3
- Figure 2: Pascal's Law Application.....5
- Figure 3: Hydraulic Lift.....5
- Figure 4: Hydraulic Brake.....5
- Figure 5: Graph.....8

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Firstly, we all likely to thank Allah Almighty who provides us knowledge, energy and skills to get opportunity and to increase our experience by completing this complex engineering problem.

We would also like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to **Sir Bilal** for his invaluable support and for teaching us these subjects in great detail. His dedication and efforts have been a source of inspiration throughout our journey.

This project and the research behind it would not have been possible without the exceptional support of any Team Member. Enthusiasm, knowledge and exacting attention to detail have been an inspiration and kept our work on.

CONTRIBUTION OF EACH TEAM MEMBER:

- **2023-IM-09:**

Model Development and Report Writing

- **2023-IM-13:**

Model Development and Analysis Support

- **2023-IM-30:**

Analysis and Writing Support

- **2023-IM-31:**

Analysis and Model Support

“Design and Working of a Hydraulic Excavator Based on Thermo-fluid Principles”

Abstract:

This report discusses the design and working of a hydraulic excavator, developed using the principles of thermo-fluid. The excavator model is constructed with basic components such as syringes, water, and cardboard to demonstrate the functionality of hydraulic systems. The model is designed to showcase how fluid pressure and thermo-fluid principles are applied in hydraulic excavators for efficient operations

Fig 1: Model

Problem Statement of OEL:

Select a system / component working on thermo fluids principle/s. Develop its model and discuss working principle. Design an experiment by using the model which utilizes its working principle where outputs and inputs are identified etc. Prepare its OEL report including detailed description of its working, working principle, perform relevant calculations and suggest possible modifications (if any).

CLO/CLOs formulated for OEL

CLO 4 / PLO-3

Analyze the selected system / component of system working on thermo fluids principle's by utilizing, as well as for enhancing their knowledge of thermo-fluids.

Justification:

An excavator works using thermos-fluid principles, mainly focusing on **hydraulics**, a part of fluid mechanics. It uses fluid flow to convert energy, apply pressure, and transfer force through hydraulic cylinders. This system uses incompressible fluids to send power from a hydraulic pump to parts like the boom, arm, and bucket, allowing smooth and powerful movements.

The hydraulic system follows **Pascal's Law**, which says that pressure in a confined fluid spreads equally in all directions. A hydraulic pump creates high-pressure fluid, which flows through valves and hoses to the cylinders. This pressure moves pistons in the cylinders, turning fluid power into mechanical energy to control the excavator's parts.

Introduction:

Hydraulic excavators are from the most widely used earthmoving equipment in construction and mining industry, and they will continue to play an important role among off-highway vehicles in years to come [2–4]. Typical operations of hydraulic excavators include grading, digging, and loading, which all require coordinated manipulation of the boom, arm, and bucket cylinders. However, operating an excavator efficiently requires skill and practice, making it a challenging task for less experienced operators.

Automated excavation systems can help beginners complete tasks faster and with good quality. Additionally, automated excavators are useful for working in dangerous or hard-to-reach places, like radiation zones or remote areas. [5-7]

Working Principle

Pascal's Law:

Statement:

Pascal's Law states that when a force is applied to a confined fluid, the pressure is transmitted equally in all directions within the fluid. [8]

Formula:

The mathematical formula is

$$P=F/A$$

According to Pascal's principle, this pressure is transmitted undiminished throughout the fluid and to all walls of the container. Thus, a pressure P_2 is felt at the other piston that is equal to P_1 . That is $P_1=P_2$

$$F_1/A_1=F_2/A_2.$$

Fig 2: Pascal's Law Application

Application of Pascal's Law:

One of the most important technological applications of Pascal's principle is found in a hydraulic system, which is an enclosed fluid system used to exert forces.

1. Hydraulic Excavator:

Hydraulic pressure moves the parts of the excavator, like the boom and bucket, to lift heavy Loads.

2. Hydraulic Lift

A hydraulic lift uses pressure from a small piston to lift heavy objects with a larger piston. It's commonly used to lift cars in repair shops.

Fig 3: Hydraulic Lift

3. Hydraulic Brake

Pressing the brake pedal sends pressure through fluid to stop the vehicle quickly

Fig 4: Hydraulic Brake

Work Done:

Work done refers to the energy transferred when a force is applied to an object, causing it to move in the direction of the force. SI unit is Joules.

$$1\text{J}=1\text{Nm}$$

Formula:

$$W=F.d$$

- **Positive Work:** When the force applied and the motion are in the same direction.
- **Negative Work:** When the force applied is in the opposite direction of the motion (e.g., when you apply brakes on a moving car).

Example:

Imagine a **hydraulic excavator**. If the hydraulic system uses a force of 500 newtons to move the bucket 2 meters, then the work done would be:

$$\text{Work Done}=500\text{ N}\times 2\text{ m}=1000\text{ Joules}$$

So, 1000 joules of energy were used to move the bucket.

Model Description:

The model consists of the following components:

- **Syringes:** Act as hydraulic cylinders.
- **Water:** The fluid used to transmit pressure.
- **Cardboard:** Used to construct the boom, arm, and bucket, mimicking the actual parts of an excavator.
- **Tubing:** Connects syringes, allowing water to flow between them.

Applications of Hydraulic Excavators:

1. Construction: Used for digging, moving dirt, and lifting heavy materials.
2. Mining: Helps dig up and move materials from mining sites.
3. Demolition: Breaks down old buildings and structures.
4. Landscaping: Moves soil and helps shape land for gardens or parks.
5. Forestry: Clears trees and bushes.
6. Waste Management: Moves and sorts waste materials at disposal sites.

Working:

- 1) A person presses the plunger of the input syringe, applying force to the fluid inside.
- 2) The force creates pressure in the fluid, calculated as $P=F/A$, where P is pressure, F is force, and A is the cross-sectional area of the input syringe.
- 3) The incompressible fluid transmits this pressure equally throughout the connected system, following Pascal's Law.
- 4) The transmitted pressure acts on the output syringe, moving its plunger. From which we calculate force on other output syring.
- 5) The motion of the output syringe converts the pressure into mechanical motion, which moves parts of the model (e.g., lifting the arm or tilting the bucket).
- 6) The model resets as the input syringe is released, and the fluid returns to its original state

Analysis of Hydraulic Excavator:

Observation and Calculation:

Input Syring (F₁):

- Diameter of 10ml syringe = $D_1 = 0.01596\text{m}$
- Area of 10ml syringe = $A_1 = \pi D_1^2/4 = 2 \times 10^{-4}\text{m}^2$

Output Syring (F₂):

- Diameter of 5ml syringe = $D_2 = 0.01246\text{m}$
- Area of 5ml syringe = $A_2 = \pi D_2^2/4 = 1.22 \times 10^{-4}\text{m}^2$

F₁ (N)	F₂=F₁.A₂/A₁ (N)
2.8	1.71
4	2.4

F₁ (N)	d₁ (m)	Work done=Force x Displacement (Nm)
2.8	1.708	0.11
4	2.4	0.23

Graph:

Fig 5: Relationship between Force and Work Done

Sample Calculation:

1. Pascal law:

We will find values of F_1 at different masses. Now we will find values of F_2 by using this formula.

$$\frac{F_1}{A_1} = \frac{F_2}{A_2}$$

- When $F_1 = 2.8\text{N}$

$$\frac{2.8}{2 \times 10^{-4}} = \frac{F_2}{1.22 \times 10^{-4}}$$

$$F_2 = 1.71\text{N}$$

- When $F_1 = 4\text{N}$

$$\frac{4.0034}{2 \times 10^{-4}} = \frac{F_2}{1.22 \times 10^{-4}}$$

$$F_2 = 2.4\text{N}$$

2. Work Done:

- Weight = $W_1 = 2.8\text{N}$
- Displacement = $d_1 = 0.0405\text{m}$

$$F_1 = W_1 = mg = 2.8\text{N}$$

$$\text{Work done} = F_1 \cdot d_1 = (2.8) \times (0.0405) = 0.11\text{Nm}$$

- Weight = $W_2 = 4\text{N}$
- Displacement = $d_2 = 0.058\text{m}$

$$F_1 = W_1 = mg = 4\text{N}$$

$$\text{Work done} = F_1 \cdot d_2 = (4) \times (0.058) = 0.23\text{Nm}$$

Result:

The experiment successfully showed how hydraulic pressure moves parts of the excavator. We used syringes filled with water to demonstrate how force is applied through the hydraulic system. Our calculations confirmed that the pressure created by the fluid allowed the model to work as expected.

- We apply a input force of about 2.8N on syring whose area is $2 \times 10^{-4}\text{m}^2$ and then we get a force on output syring which is about 1.71N.
- At 2.8N load the displacement is 1.71m from which we calculated work done which is about 0.11Nm. Similarly at 4N load the work done is 0.23Nm.
- The graph shows a **linear relationship** between force and work done. As the applied force increases, the work done also increases proportionally.

Comment:

This project highlights the effectiveness of hydraulic systems in simplifying heavy tasks. The model provided a clear understanding of the principles. It allowed us to apply the principles of fluid mechanics to a real-world machine like an excavator. The teamwork was key in completing the model and understanding how the hydraulic system operates. The idea of adding a second pump to save energy could be a helpful improvement for real hydraulic systems, making them more environmentally friendly and efficient.

Modification:

Nowadays the improvement of energy efficiency and the reduction of pollutant emissions are the major challenges that the mobile machinery manufacturers have to face with. With rising fuel prices and increasingly stringent regulations, the development of energy saving solutions and efficient hydraulic system have become a priority for researchers and OEM's. One of the most effective approach is the machine hybridization but other solutions can be adopted.

Hybrid excavator, engine output is converted into both electrical and hydraulic energy, energy conversion and transmission losses are reduced and kinetic energy of the upper structure is regenerated. [9]

Energy loss

- Heat Dissipation due to fluid flow resistance and energy transformations.
- When the hydraulic pump generates flow even when no action is needed.

Energy saving solution

- Introducing a second pump allows more precise flow control and reduces unnecessary energy consumption.
- During downward movements, the potential energy of the boom and arm can be recovered and stored using hydraulic accumulators or electrical storage systems. This energy can later be reused.
- Achieved a 15% reduction in fuel consumption by optimizing flow management, recovering energy, and utilizing hybrid components.

Adding a second pump to a hydraulic system does not waste energy, instead, it optimizes energy use by enabling more efficient power management. Here how it benefits the system:

Key Benefits of a Second Pump

- **Task Division and Efficiency:**
The workload is divided between the pumps, with each handling specific tasks (e.g., high-pressure for lifting, low-pressure for steering). This ensures neither pump is overworked, reducing energy losses due to inefficiency.
- **Reduced Throttling Losses:**
In single-pump systems, excess flow is often throttled through valves, wasting energy. A second pump allows precise delivery of fluid where needed, minimizing throttling and associated losses.
- **Energy Savings in Low Demand Scenarios:**
When only low-pressure operations are needed, the second pump can take over, letting the main pump operate at reduced capacity, saving energy and reducing fuel consumption.
- **Enhanced System Reliability:**
The second pump provides redundancy. If one pump fails, the other can handle part of the workload, ensuring system continuity and preventing downtime

It can decrease overall energy consumption and extend the lifespan of the engine and hydraulic components.

Challenges for Power Supply

- **Increased Initial Demand:**
Adding a second pump may require additional power from the engine to operate under peak conditions, especially if both pumps are running simultaneously at maximum capacity.
- **System Complexity:**
The inclusion of a second pump increases the complexity of the hydraulic system, requiring more precise control mechanisms, which can place additional demands on the power management system.

Reference:

[1] "Thermal Energy Systems: Design and Analysis" by S.G. Penoncello

[2] Hao W. E. N., Analysis report of 2010 excavator market in China, *Construction Machinery Technology & Management*. (2011) **2**, article 23. [Google Scholar](#)

[3] Ni T., Zhang H., Yu C., Zhao D., and Liu S., Design of highly realistic virtual environment for excavator simulator, *Computers and Electrical Engineering*. (2013) **39**, no. 7, 2112–2123, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2013.06.010>, 2-s2.0-84885586799.

Web of Science®Google Scholar

[4] Global excavator market report: 2014 edition, 2014. [Google Scholar](#)

[5] Stentz A., Bares J., Singh S., and Rowe P., A robotic excavator for autonomous truck loading, *Autonomous Robots*. (1999) **7**, no. 2, 175–186, <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1008914201877>, 2-s2.0-0033344027. [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)

[6] Singh S., State of the art in automation of earthmoving, *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*. (1997) **10**, no. 4, 179–188, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0893-1321\(1997\)10:4\(179\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0893-1321(1997)10:4(179)), 2-s2.0-0031257406. [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)

[7] Yu H., Liu Y., and Hasan M. S., Review of modelling and remote control for excavators, *International Journal of Advanced Mechatronic Systems*. (2010) **2**, no. 1-2, 68–80, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJAMechS.2010.03085>, 2-s2.0-84856544461. [Google Scholar](#)

[8] <https://www.vedantu.com/physics/pascal-law>

[9] Rossetti A., Macor A., 2013. Multi-objective optimization of hydro-mechanical power split transmissions. *Mechanism and Machine Theory*; 62(4), 112–128. DOI:10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2012.11.009